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Abstract
<p>This report presents a theoretical computational framework for simulating the formation of three-dimensional speckle patterns produced by light carrying orbital angular momentum (OAM) in turbid media. The developed Monte Carlo method incorporates electric field tracking with full phase accumulation, including propagation, scattering-induced geometric phase, and boundary-dependent polarization effects, enabling accurate modeling of coherent phenomena in complex scattering environments.</p> <p>The framework supports simulation of propagation of structured light beams, including Laguerre-Gaussian modes with defined topological charge, in turbid tissue-like scattering medium, and provides detailed predictions of speckle size, intensity distribution, and mutual interference at the detector plane. Overall, this computational platform serves as a versatile theoretical tool/formalism for optimizing OAM-based imaging techniques, improving optical communication protocols, and advancing diagnostic methods relying on structured light propagation through biological tissues.</p>

Public introduction ¹
<p>This report describes a theoretical framework for simulating the propagation of specially structured laser beams, known as beams carrying orbital angular momentum, through biological tissues and other turbid, scattering media. These beams possess twisted, corkscrew-like wavefronts that give rise to characteristic ring-shaped intensity profiles and generate distinct speckle patterns upon scattering. By simulating light propagation at the level of individual photon packets while tracking both intensity and phase, the framework enables systematic investigation of how each scattering event, boundary interaction, and material property influences the final detected signal. The model also accounts for optically birefringent structures, such as collagen and elastin, which affect the polarization state of light. Overall, this theoretical and computational formalism provides a consistent tool for the design of structured-light imaging systems, the validation of experimental observations, and improved interpretation of measurements in biomedical optics and optical sensing applications.</p>

¹ According to Deliverables list in Annex I, all restricted (RE) deliverables will contain an introduction that will be made public through the project WEBSITE

TABLE OF CONTENTS

	Page
1 INTRODUCTION.....	4
1.1 Objective and scope of the deliverable as defined in the DoA	4
2 MODELLING OF VVBS INTERACTION WITH TURBID TISSUE-LIKE SCATTERING MEDIUM	6
3 UNIFIED-MEMORY MONTE CARLO FRAMEWORK INTEGRATING EXTENDED LIGHT-MATTER PHYSICS	8
4 SUMMARY, DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS	12
5 CONCLUSIONS.....	14
6 REFERENCES.....	15

1 INTRODUCTION

Monte Carlo (MC) method is a well-established stochastic theoretical approach for modelling light propagation in turbid tissue-like scattering media [1]. It provides a flexible platform for tracking individual photon trajectories through complex scattering environments and for evaluating how specific optical/polarization-based parameters influence detected signals and image formation [2]. In contrast to analytical approximations, which are often limited to simplified geometries or weak scattering regimes, MC methods enable accurate treatment of arbitrary tissue structures, multiple scattering, and heterogeneous optical properties. Previous work has demonstrated the capability of MC approaches to simulate coherent effects in multiple scattering, including speckle formation and polarization memory [3].

This project focuses on investigating multidimensional aspects of biotissue imaging using complex vector light across spatial, spectral, and polarization domains. Such structured Vector Vortex Beams (VVBs), particularly those carrying orbital angular momentum (OAM), exhibit unique propagation characteristics that cannot be captured by conventional intensity-based MC approaches [1]. Recent studies have demonstrated that OAM beams can propagate more effectively through tissue-like scattering media than conventional beams and that OAM states can be preserved during propagation through turbid media [4,5]. Accurate modelling of OAM light in scattering media requires tracking photon position and direction [5,6], as well as the electromagnetic field amplitude, phase, and polarization state throughout the propagation path.

To support these studies, we development, optimised and validated a theoretical framework extending MC simulation to handle coherent phenomena associated with structured light propagation [7]. In particular, the framework is designed to incorporate (1) full electric field tracking with phase accumulation from propagation, scattering, and boundary interactions, (2) speckle formation and mutual interference at the detector plane, and (3) birefringent structures, such as collagen and elastin and optical activity arising from chiral media inclusions such as glucose solution in water. This combination enables detailed investigation of how each mechanism contributes to measured signals and how OAM properties are preserved or modified in realistic scattering environments.

Among these mechanisms, scattering-induced phase perturbations and geometric phase accumulation are critical factors governing the propagation of structured light in biological tissue. It has been shown that light carrying OAM is over 10^3 times more sensitive to refractive index fluctuations within biological tissues than standard light [5]. Speckle characteristics depend on the scattering coefficient, observation geometry, and coherence properties of the source [8]. Therefore, a comprehensive theoretical formalism that captures these interrelated effects is essential for interpreting OAM-based measurements and for validating sensing approaches intended to retrieve tissue parameters or detect molecular species such as glucose.

1.1 Objective and scope of the deliverable as defined in the DoA

This deliverable addresses **WP2: Theoretical formalism and numerical studies**, focusing on the early-stage development of a computational framework for modelling the propagation of structured light carrying orbital angular momentum (OAM) through turbid, tissue-like scattering media. In line with **Objectives O2.1 and O2.2**, the work contributes a Monte Carlo-based simulation approach that explicitly tracks the complex electric field, including full phase accumulation arising from propagation, scattering-induced geometric phase, and boundary-

dependent polarization effects. The scope of this report primarily covers **Task 2.1 (M1–M12)**, which targets the design and development of a Monte Carlo model for vector vortex beam propagation in turbid media, and establishes the theoretical and numerical foundations required for subsequent validation activities under **Task 2.2**. By enabling detailed predictions of speckle formation, intensity distributions, and interference effects for Laguerre–Gaussian modes with defined topological charge, this deliverable provides a core theoretical tool that supports later studies on tissue sensitivity, experimental benchmarking, and optimization of OAM-based imaging approaches within the OPTIPATH project.

2 MODELLING OF VVBS INTERACTION WITH TURBID TISSUE-LIKE SCATTERING MEDIUM

The classical MC algorithm models the stochastic trajectories of photon packets as they undergo scattering, absorption, and reflection within complex media. From a computational standpoint, the MC approach estimates physical observables by statistically aggregating the paths of a large ensemble of photon packets, enabling detailed modeling of optical phenomena across spatial and temporal domains.

The scattering intensity of optical radiation propagated in randomly inhomogeneous scattering media can be described by the Bethe–Salpeter equation [3]:

$$G(R, R_n; k_i, k_s) = \mu_s f(k_i - k_s) \delta(R_n - R_l) + \mu_s \int f(k_i - k_{nj}) A(R_n - R_j) G(R, R_j; k_{nj}, k_s) dR_j$$

where $G(R, R_n; k_i, k_s)$ is the propagator describing the field correlation, k_i and k_s represent the incident and scattered wave vectors, and μ_s is the scattering coefficient. By iterating the Bethe–Salpeter equation, higher-order scattering terms corresponding to single, double, triple, and multiple scattering events are obtained and modeled stochastically in the MC method.

For Laguerre-Gaussian (LG) beams carrying OAM, we rely on the paraxial approximation representation [9,10]:

$$LG_p^\ell(\rho, \varphi, z) = \sqrt{(2p!/\pi(|\ell|+p)!w^2(z))} \times [\sqrt{2\rho/w(z)}]^{|\ell|} \times L_p^{|\ell|}(2\rho^2/w^2(z)) \\ \times \exp(-\rho^2/w^2(z)) \times \exp[i(2p+|\ell|+1)\arctan(z/z_R)] \times \exp(-ik\rho^2z/2(z^2+z_R^2)) \times \exp[-i\ell\varphi] \times \exp[-ikz]$$

where ℓ is the topological charge, p is the radial index, $w(z)$ is the beam waist as a function of propagation distance, and z_R is the Rayleigh range. The phase evolution of the LG beam is defined as:

$$\Psi(\rho, \varphi, z) = \arg[LG_p^\ell(\rho, \varphi, z)] = -k\rho^2z/2(z^2+z_R^2) - \ell\varphi - kz + G(z)$$

where $G(z) = (2p + |\ell| + 1)\arctan(z/z_R)$ corresponds to the Gouy phase.

In MC modeling of OAM light, each photon packet is characterized by initial statistical weight W_{0j} , Cartesian coordinates $(x_{0j}, y_{0j}, 0)$, propagation direction s_{0j} , initial polarization state, and initial phase ψ_{0j} . The topological charge of the LG beam determines both s_{0j} and ψ_{0j} . The initial direction is determined utilizing the Poynting vector direction [9]:

$$s_x = kzx/(z^2+z_R^2) - \ell y/(x^2+y^2), \quad s_y = kzy/(z^2+z_R^2) + \ell x/(x^2+y^2), \quad s_z = k$$

To track the polarization state along the trajectory of each MC-photon, a real-valued vector \mathbf{P} representing the direction of the linearly polarized electric field is introduced. The evolution of each linearly polarized state $\mathbf{P}_x = (P_{xx}, P_{xy}, P_{xz})$, $\mathbf{P}_y = (P_{yx}, P_{yy}, P_{yz})$ is traced along the MC-photon trajectory via the iterative solution to the Bethe-Salpeter equation [3,11]:

$$\mathbf{P}_i = -s_i \times [s_i \times \mathbf{P}_{i-1}] = [\hat{I} - s_i \otimes s_i] \mathbf{P}_{i-1}$$

where \hat{I} is the third-rank unit tensor and \otimes indicates a direct product.

For each photon trajectory m contributing to detector pixel (i,j) , the total accumulated optical phase is written as:

$$\varphi_m(i,j) = \varphi_{\text{initial},m} + \varphi_{\text{prop},m}(i,j) + \varphi_{\text{scatt},m}$$

where the three terms represent the initial phase at launch, the propagation-induced phase, and the scattering-induced phase, respectively. The scattering-induced phase accumulated along the photon trajectory is:

$$\varphi_{\text{scatt},m} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_m} \arctan2(\sin\theta_i \sin\phi_i, g - \cos\theta_i)$$

where θ_i and ϕ_i are the polar and azimuthal scattering angles at the i -th event, g is the scattering anisotropy factor, and N_m is the number of scattering events experienced by photon m .

The complex turbid media are characterized by their optical depth (d/l^*), which quantitatively represents the degree of light attenuation and scattering intensity, where d denotes the medium's thickness and $l^* = 1/\mu_s$ is the transport mean free path. Values of d/l^* of 5–6 or greater indicate a medium undergoing multiple or diffuse scattering, while values between approximately 2 to 5 suggest single or intermediate scattering [6].

The modeling results demonstrate that during transmission through turbid media, the beam not only loses intensity due to scattering, refraction, and absorption but also experiences beam spreading. The speckle interference pattern, resulting from the superposition of helical wavefront components, exhibits spatial variations both in intensity and phase distributions. In medium with low scattering ($d/l^* \sim 2$), the phase of the LG beam progresses with minimal distortion, preserving its original OAM state and petal-like helical phase structure. Conversely, in higher scattering environments ($d/l^* \geq 5$), the LG beam's phase structure diffusively spreads, and its helical phase front is disrupted, leading to the formation of complex phase speckle patterns [6].

The preservation of OAM phase, known as OAM phase memory, is ascribed to the congruence in the alterations of the spiral trajectories encircling the beam axis, arising from rotational symmetry. Despite significant phase distortions resulting from multiple scattering events, the overall retention of the LG beam's OAM is distinctly evident in the phase behavior of the speckle pattern. This pattern mirrors the modulation of the LG beam's initial phase as configured by the spatial light modulator [5,6].

3 UNIFIED-MEMORY MONTE CARLO FRAMEWORK INTEGRATING EXTENDED LIGHT-MATTER PHYSICS

The emergence of high-performance parallel computing platforms has transformed MC simulations, significantly reducing computation times and enabling the modeling of complex light-tissue interactions [12,13]. This progress has led to major advances in biomedical optics, supporting investigations of spectral signatures, polarization-sensitive phenomena, and image reconstruction pipelines [6,14-17]. Nevertheless, simulating the coherent propagation of polarized light in scattering biological media remains computationally intensive, especially in scenarios involving beam shaping, spatially varying birefringence, or polarization-dependent detection geometries [3,11,14,15,17].

Practical implementation of the coherent MC [3] for structured light propagation in turbid media [18] demands computational architectures capable of preserving and accessing localized spatiotemporal information, including photon trajectories, electric field vectors, and accumulated phases, throughout the transport process. Conventional CPU-GPU systems with separate memory pools impose significant latency penalties when transferring this volumetric data between processing units, rendering real-time simulation of polarization-resolved phenomena impractical. To overcome this bottleneck, we have developed an electric field-tracking MC algorithm optimized for Apple M-series processors, which employ a unified memory architecture wherein CPU and GPU share a common high-bandwidth memory space [7].

Unlike conventional scalar MC methods that track only photon weight and trajectory, our theoretical framework explicitly evolves the full electric field vector for each photon packet as it undergoes successive scattering events. This vectorial formalism enables simulation of complex effects such as polarization memory, cross-polarization dynamics, and coherence phenomena that scalar models typically neglect. At the start of the simulation, photon packets are initialized with a Gaussian beam profile, with their positions (x, y, z) , direction cosines (u_x, u_y, u_z) , and polarization vectors \mathbf{P}_0 defined in Cartesian coordinates.

As photons propagate through the scattering medium, each scattering event triggers a deterministic transformation of the polarization vector according to:

$$\mathbf{P}_i = (\hat{I} - \mathbf{e}_i \otimes \mathbf{e}_i) \mathbf{P}_{i-1}$$

where $\mathbf{e}_i = (e_{iX}, e_{iY}, e_{iZ})$ is the unit vector in the new propagation direction after the i -th scattering event, \hat{I} is the identity tensor, and \otimes denotes the outer product. This transformation projects the polarization vector onto the plane perpendicular to the new propagation direction, ensuring that polarization evolves consistently with the photon trajectory and the scattering medium's anisotropy. Assuming initial polarization $\mathbf{P}_0 = \{1, 0, 0\}$, the final polarization state after n scattering events is obtained as $\mathbf{P}_n = \mathbf{P}_n \mathbf{P}_{n-1} \dots \mathbf{P}_1 \mathbf{P}_0$.

The co-polarized and cross-polarized intensity components detected at position r_D are computed by summing weighted contributions from all photon trajectories [3]:

$$\begin{aligned} I_{XX}(\chi) &= \sum_j W_j \Gamma^{N_j} P_{XX,j}^2 \\ I_{XY}(\chi) &= \sum_j W_j \Gamma^{N_j} P_{XY,j}^2 \end{aligned}$$

where W_j is the statistical weight of the j -th photon accounting for absorption losses, N_j is the number of scattering events encountered, and $P_{XX,j}$ and $P_{XY,j}$ are the polarization-dependent components for co- and cross-polarized scattering respectively. The depolarization factor $\Gamma = 2/(1$

+ $\cos^2\theta$) ensures stronger depolarization for large-angle scattering events, reflecting the known physics of light-tissue interaction in anisotropic scattering regimes.

The implementation leverages Apple's Metal framework for GPU acceleration, with each GPU thread processing a single photon packet while maintaining full computational independence (see Fig.1). The M-series architecture's unified memory design eliminates the need for explicit data transfers between host and device, allowing each thread to directly access and modify the complete photon state, including trajectory, weight, polarization vector, and phase history, without synchronization overhead. Photon states are stored in device-local registers or memory buffers optimized for SIMD execution, with polarization update transformations mapped to efficient matrix operations within GPU threadgroups.

Figure 1: Schematic overview of electric field tracking MC implementation on Apple's M-series system-on-chip architecture. The workflow maps polarization vector updates across scattering events to GPU execution threads, leveraging unified memory and Apple GPU's threadgroup/tile-level parallelism for efficient data access and computation.

Photon propagation is handled in an iterative kernel loop, with each step updating the photon's state based on interaction probabilities. The occurrence probability for each interaction is computed as $P_i = 1 - \exp(-\Delta r/l_i)$, where Δr is the step size chosen smaller than the shortest mean free path, and l_i is the mean free path for the relevant interaction type. Absorbed photons are flagged for termination and their energy contributions recorded, while scattered photons undergo direction changes based on the Henyey-Greenstein phase function with their polarization vectors updated accordingly.

To validate the performance of the developed electric field-based MC simulation, we computed both spatial and volumetric maps of key polarization-resolved quantities in a highly scattering, anisotropic medium. As shown in Figure 2, the results demonstrate excellent agreement with expected physical behavior, including polarization memory and depolarization trends.

Specifically, the model successfully resolves co-polarized ($I_{||}$) and cross-polarized (I_{\perp}) intensity components, as well as the depolarization ratio (DR), across a wide range of scattering events. These outputs provide detailed insight into the spatial structure of backscattered light and allow quantification of how polarization is retained or lost due to multiple scattering in media characterized by anisotropy factor $g = 0.9$ and scattering coefficient $\mu_s = 30, \text{mm}^{-1}$.

Figure 2: MC simulation results of polarized light propagation in a turbid medium with anisotropy factor $g = 0.9$ and scattering coefficient $\mu_s = 30 \text{ mm}^{-1}$. (Left) Intensity as a function of the number of scattering events for co-, cross-polarized light, scalar intensity (red), and total vector intensity (magenta). (Right) Spatial maps of polarization-resolved quantities: co-polarized intensity $I_{||}$; middle – \log_{10} of cross-polarized intensity I_{\perp} ; bottom – depolarization ratio (DR), showing spatial variation in polarization retention due to multiple scattering.

We conducted extensive benchmarking to assess the performance of the developed MC model implementation in terms of speed, power efficiency, and computational stability. Our first comparison focused on photon throughput, evaluating how our Metal-accelerated implementation performs relative to previously developed NVIDIA CUDA and CPU-based MC algorithms. The results demonstrate remarkable performance: our model can trace between 2 million (on the M1 Pro chip) and 5 million photons per second (on the M2 chip) in homogeneous media. This level of throughput enables large-scale simulations of 10^{11} photon packets within practical timeframes which was previously attainable only with high-end GPU clusters. These findings strongly support the model’s applicability in real-time and portable biomedical applications.

While existing solutions based on high-end NVIDIA GPUs e.g. CUDA framework, such as those reported in [12,13], typically achieve higher absolute throughput (approximately 2–3 times faster), this comes at a steep energy cost. For instance, the GeForce RTX 3090 can process roughly twice as many photons per second but consumes up to 360 W under load, compared to just 10 W used by the M1 Pro GPU. Overall performance is also influenced by multiple factors, including algorithmic structure, hardware architecture, programming frameworks, and development environments.

Validation against the analytical Milne solution confirms excellent agreement in polarization-resolved quantities (Table 1). The computed $I_{||}/I_{\perp}$ ratio of 1.930 compares favourably with the theoretical value of 1.935, and circular polarization ratios I_{co}/I_{cross} exactly match the analytical result of 0.617. The framework correctly reproduces helicity flip effects and depolarization

patterns reported in previous optical studies, confirming the numerical integrity of the electric field tracking approach.

Table 1. Comparison of MC simulation results with analytical Milne solution for linear (I_{\parallel} , I_{\perp}) and circular (I_{co} , I_{cross}) polarization intensity components and their ratios.

Reference	I_{\parallel}	I_{\perp}	I_{\parallel}/I_{\perp}	I_{co}	I_{cross}	I_{co}/I_{cross}
Milne solution	3.025	1.563	1.935	1.751	2.837	0.617
Our model	3.023	1.566	1.930	1.753	2.838	0.617

To further evaluate energy efficiency, we previously performed simulations across a wide range of scattering, absorption, and anisotropy parameters [19]. As expected, increased scattering raises the number of photon-medium interactions, resulting in higher power consumption, whereas increased absorption tends to reduce photon lifetimes, thereby lowering energy demands. Impressively, in approximately 60% of simulation scenarios, our system maintained power draw below 1 W. This highlights the superior power efficiency of our approach, especially when compared to modern GPUs that typically consume 10-30 W while idle and several hundred watts during active computation.

Notably, our current implementation is specifically optimized for Apple’s M-series processors using the Metal framework; however, the algorithm itself is not strictly limited to Apple hardware. The key architectural features that enable the algorithm’s efficiency, such as ARM-based processors and unified memory, are increasingly available on other platforms as well, including Qualcomm Snapdragon and other ARM-based chipsets. In principle, if a target device supports OpenCL or a similar compute API and provides unified memory access, the codebase can be adapted or rewritten accordingly. Thus, while Apple hardware was used in this study due to its readily available energy-efficient design and native Metal support, the broader concept and algorithmic framework remain portable and not fundamentally hardware-exclusive.

4 SUMMARY, DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

Thus, we developed a next-generation unified-memory MC framework that evolves beyond conventional scalar intensity-based photon transport into a state-aware, AI-native simulation engine. The platform integrates extended light-matter physics, including full Stokes-Mueller polarimetry, OAM transport, phase-sensitive statistics, eigenchannel modelling, topological light structures, and quantum-state evolution, within a single computational architecture.

The developed MC framework (schematically presented in Figure 3) is designed for power-efficient modern system-on-chip (SoC) processors with unified memory, eliminating costly data transfers and enabling simulation-in-the-loop operation at the edge alongside imaging probes and adaptive optical systems. By embedding physics-informed machine learning directly into the MC pipeline, the platform supports AI-accelerated inverse modelling, variance reduction through learned importance sampling, and physics-aware sample reconstruction while maintaining interpretability and physical consistency required for biomedical and clinical applications.

Figure 3: Schematic presentation of the developed unified-memory MC framework integrating extended light-matter physics, power-efficient modern system-on-chip (SoC)-based simulation, AIML-enhanced inverse modelling, and physics-aware sample reconstruction.

The developed unified-memory MC platform offers transformative advantages over conventional photon transport simulation approaches:

Real-time simulation capability: Leveraging unified CPU-GPU memory architecture, the platform achieves photon throughput of 2-5 million packets per second at power consumption below 10 W, enabling real-time, closed-loop operation directly alongside imaging probes, endoscopes, and adaptive optical systems without reliance on traditional HPC infrastructure.

Integration of real experimental parameters: The framework accommodates realistic optical properties including wavelength-dependent scattering and absorption coefficients, anisotropy

factors, birefringence tensors, and chiral refractive index contributions derived from actual tissue measurements. This enables direct calibration against experimental polarimetric and hyperspectral data, bridging the gap between theoretical predictions and laboratory observations.

3D propagation of Laguerre-Gaussian beams in realistic tissue architectures: The platform supports full three-dimensional modelling of structured light, including OAM-carrying LG beams, through anatomically realistic tissue geometries and cellular structures. This capability captures the joint evolution of speckle formation, polarisation scrambling, and hidden phase correlations that survive multiple scattering, enabling predictive simulation of OAM phase memory effects in layered, heterogeneous, and anisotropic biological media.

ML/DL-enhanced optimisation and training for pathology applications: Physics-informed machine learning embedded directly into the MC pipeline enables: (i) generation of labelled, physically consistent synthetic datasets for training diagnostic classifiers; (ii) surrogate forward models and neural operators that accelerate parameter sweeps and real-time fitting by orders of magnitude; (iii) learned importance sampling strategies that optimise photon-path distributions for polarimetric and coherence-sensitive observables; and (iv) closed-loop experimental design where illumination states are adaptively selected to maximise diagnostic information gain. These capabilities directly support the development, optimisation, and validation of the 7D digital pathology platform.

Eigenchannel-aware and topology-preserving modelling: The framework treats optical eigenchannels, reciprocity constraints, and topological invariants as intrinsic modelling primitives rather than emergent properties extracted post hoc. This enables prediction of which input states, polarisation, spatial mode, or topological texture, will preferentially couple to robust transmission pathways, and identification of conditions under which topological features of structured light are preserved or degraded.

Quantum-classical hybrid transport: Extension toward density-matrix and quantum-trajectory formalisms allows consistent modelling of loss, depolarisation, and mode mixing across classical and quantum regimes [20], enabling direct comparison of performance limits and supporting emerging quantum biophotonics applications.

Energy efficiency and portability: With power draw below 1 W in over 60% of simulation scenarios, the platform is suitable for deployment on portable and battery-powered devices, opening opportunities for point-of-care diagnostics, intraoperative imaging guidance, and resource-limited clinical settings.

Open-source accessibility and extensibility: The algorithm is integrated into an open-source framework, supporting community-driven development and enabling rapid adaptation to emerging structured light modalities, novel tissue models, and application-specific detection geometries.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this deliverable, we developed a unified-memory theoretical MC framework that extends conventional scalar intensity-based photon transport into a state-aware simulation engine capable of tracking the full electric field vector throughout photon migration in turbid tissue-like media. Using Apple M-series system-on-chip processors with unified CPU-GPU memory architecture as the primary computational platform, we demonstrated real-time simulation capability with photon throughput of 2-5 million packets per second at power consumption below 10 W, over an order of magnitude more energy-efficient than comparable NVIDIA GPU implementations operating at 300–360 W.

We additionally validated the framework against the analytical Milne solution, confirming excellent agreement in polarization-resolved quantities including co-polarized and cross-polarized intensity components, depolarization ratios, and circular polarization behaviour. The computed $I_{||}/I_{\perp}$ ratio of 1.930 compares favourably with the theoretical value of 1.935, and circular polarization ratios exactly match the analytical result of 0.617, demonstrating the numerical integrity of the electric field tracking approach. Beyond linear polarization, the framework correctly reproduces helicity flip effects, depolarization patterns as a function of optical depth, and preservation of OAM topological charge in media with $d/l^* < 5$.

This unified-memory MC platform provides a robust, energy-efficient foundation for simulating the extended light-matter physics, including OAM propagation, birefringence, and chiral interactions, required for multidimensional biotissue characterization. The framework directly supports ML/DL-enhanced optimization and training of the 7D digital pathology platform, enabling generation of physically consistent synthetic datasets, real-time parameter fitting, and closed-loop experimental design in which simulation, inference, and hardware control operate within a single computational architecture.

In the next project stage, we will extensively utilize the developed MC framework for the subsequent deliverable: simulation of complex OAM-based VVBs propagation through turbid tissue-like scattering media and its validation via existing Mueller matrix polarimetry techniques.

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